

Leadership Strategy as a Strategic Change Management Practices and Performance of the County Government of West Pokot, Kenya

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effect of leadership strategy on performance of the County Government of West Pokot. The study employed the following theories applicable to the study; Dennison Culture Profile Theory, Kanter Theory of Change Management. This study adopted descriptive research design. The target population of the study was the senior managers from the County government of West Pokot with a target population of 70 respondents. Data was collected using structured questionnaires and analysed and summarized using SPSS version 28. Pilot study was done in the County Government of Elgeyo Marakwet to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. The study adopted a multiple regression analysis to test the significance levels of one variable over another. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was also be used. The study found out that leadership strategy ($\mu=3.838$, $\sigma=0.921$), significantly influenced the performance of the County Government of West Pokot. The independent variable of leadership strategy influenced independently the performance of the County Government. Leadership strategy was found to have a strong positive relationship with performance of County Government of West Pokot. Further, 88.1% of the variation in the dependent variable (Performance of County Government of West Pokot) could be explained by independent variable (leadership strategy as depicted by $R^2=0.881$). It was recommended that the County Government should embrace task-oriented leadership who focuses on adapting to change in the environment, improving strategic decisions, major changes in processes, increasing flexibility and innovation and committing to change to accomplishing the task, maintaining orderly reliable operations and efficient utilization of resources .

Keywords: leadership strategy, study employed, County Government, environment, improving strategic decisions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizations are increasingly embracing the practices of adopting change management in an anticipation that this would translate to improved performance and subsequent achievement of organizational goals (Kingori, et al.,2023). Similar trends have been observed in government parastatals in Kenya that seek to employ change management practices as a means of improving their efficiency and effectiveness (Ongera, 2018). However, Nyambeke (2020) observe that most of the counties experience challenges of limited resources and investment in the implementation of change management practices is viewed with a lot of scepticisms in regard to its relevance to organizational performance. As a result, the Government of Kenya, through the presidential taskforce on reforms came up with various reforms and transformation strategies to enhance the performance of state organizations.

Every organization goes through changes every day, but because most businesses and people view changes as unusual or bad, they may or may not be aware of them (Ha, 2014). Change is a crucial component of success if it is purposefully established, properly implemented, and adapted. A change in an organization's strategy can affect how it functions, affecting everything from the organizational structure to employees' everyday activities (Bubenik et al., 2022). Yet, when badly managed and implemented, change becomes difficult to adopt and increases employee resistance, incurring large costs and risks for potential profits and goal accomplishments (Tang, 2019). As several authors demonstrate that strategic change significantly affects organizational performance (Makina & Kengara, 2018, Kim & Choi, 2022, Le & Kroll, 2017, Machimbi1 & Kilika, 2022). Internal and external environment is crucial for making a sensible plan for the change. (Kujala, 2022 & Dutta, 2018). In today's fast-paced and highly competitive marketplace, businesses that do not grow and adapt risk falling behind or going out of business (Rossi & Sengupta, 2022, Makina & Kengara, 2018 & Capssa et al., 2022). Organizational managers confront a number of challenges while implementing change, including employee resistance, potential resource and profit loss, unhappiness, and a lack of understanding of the significance of strategic change and the adaptation process inside the business. However, it is certain that studying strategic management contributes significantly to the organization's ability to grasp the weak points of strategic change and adaptability. In order to determine the empirical and theoretical

The performance of an organization is positively impacted by the presence of change management practices which tend to create a significant contribution on organizational competencies, and this in turn becomes a great boost for further enhancing innovativeness (Anantharaman, 2013). According to Horngren (2018) change management is an approach which requires interpretation and adaptation by practitioners to ensure the most suitable fit between business strategies and plans. Thus, the overall themes of change management are the integration of all institutional functions, adherence to broad organization goals and responsiveness to the external environment (Mutahi et al., 2023). In today's business environment, change is constant and organizational leaders who anticipate change and react rapidly and responsibly are successful (Westenholz, 2018). Change is often a complex and difficult process but at the same time, it is inevitable. According to Routledge (2019) organizational performance is positively impacted by the presence of change management practices which tend to create a significant contribution on organizational competencies and this in turn becomes a great boost for further enhancing innovativeness. Therefore, organizations link the maximization of performance with change management practices

The business landscape of the 21st century is characterized by rapid change brought about due to technological, economic, political and social changes (Mutahi et al., 2023). How organisations react, operate and adapt to any strategic changes determine the survivability of the company. Change is an inevitable process whether at a personal level or in organization. In a world of new technologies, shifting demographics, changing economies, fluctuating consumer preferences, reforming governments as well as dynamic competition organizations have no choice but to decide as to which direction to change (Payne, et al., (2022). Just as living things, organizational change is unconditional. An organization has to constantly align itself with the external environments through reacting to external event or through realigning the business in which it operates in (Delaby 2021).

The leap in complexity, connectivity, interdependency, and speed, compared to 20 or 30 years ago, has created an environment that is radically different and requires new approaches to change (Worley & Mohrman, 2014). Change management (CM) signifies both the theory and the practice of transforming organisations in order to adapt and thrive in a dynamic atmosphere, as well as the study of how individuals within changing organisations cope (Payne, et al., (2022). Organizational change seeks better alternatives of utilizing the capabilities and resources so as to enhance the organization's ability of increasing productivity and improve stakeholder returns (Lambertson, 2018). Whether the intended change is from a less participative, corporate culture or along some other dimension, the process tends to follow a certain pattern (Gordon, 2011).

According to Phillips, et al., (2023), strategic change management has recently been utilized by most organizations to attain a competitive edge in the constantly changing business environment. The main aspects that have contributed to this dynamism include the introduction of new strategy implementation mechanisms, adoption of new technologies by firms, increased need to resource mobilization and the increasing need for proper organizational leadership. All these have made it necessary for the county governments to adjust their operations in order to fit within the environment. The Kenyan Constitution 2010 birthed the new devolved government which consists of the forty-seven County Governments together with the national government whose aim is to bring the government closer to the grassroots' level. The county governments

strive to downstream resources to the most common citizen with an aim of promoting democratic and accountable exercise of power as well as ensuring local and national resources are shared equitably (African Development Bank Report, 2008). This could be attained through adoption of suitable strategic change management practices. As per Lambertson (2018), the process of change management is extremely important since it is a structured process designed to facilitate the transitioning of people, groups as well as an organization's present circumstance to a better and improved state. This mechanism involves the organization defining new values and behaviours, roles and positions among its workers so as to prepare them for the new changes and to cement goal congruence and a common vision between an organization and its customers (Khaw et al. 2022).

The likelihood for success in organizational and strategic change management practices is influenced by the structure of the organization and culture, especially if the culture is well aligned with the mission and vision of the organization (Schein, 2009). Though culture is resistant to change, it also makes it possible for an organization to embrace change regardless of how fast a product needs to be developed or whether there is an organized reduction in costs. Otherwise, when companies incorporate the ideas and energy aimed as organizational change, then as long as the changes structures are culturally aligned, then the initiatives become more sustainable. Experienced managers responsible for facilitating the change process are often aware of how to manage the change and the best practices of the organizations, and therefore, they do their best to maximize the company's existing culture.

Strategic change management occurrence in an organisation is a precursor of different factors. The dynamic and competitive nature of the business environment demands that the business strategic change management practices needed for attainment of competitive advantage. The firms' orientation towards the adoption of strategic change management practices is greatly influenced by factors such as implementation of strategy, leadership and governance as well as resource allocation.

Hellril and Slocum (2017), argue that management of Change requires embracement from leaders as well as staff who are compassionate. Keeping in mind that change is inevitable, the management has to develop a change management plan that guides the workers on which path to take so as to reach to a permanent change. Change is the act of becoming different or the effect of something being modified (Schnackenberg et al., 2019). To get out of our comfort zone, we have to accept that we will have to accept change (Sidikova, 2011). Armstrong (2019) defined business change as the redesign of company processes, the enhancement of its goods and/or services, and organizational changes to organizational structure and/or culture that are believed required for greater performance in the workplace. Over the past years, governments have been known to centralize power. However, a growing number of countries both in the developed and lately developing world have in the last three decades been keen on decentralizing the administrative, political and fiscal functions of the central government to sub national governments and other agencies so as to improve service delivery (Calamai, 2009). These countries include the United Kingdom, the United States, India, the former USSR, Italy, Spain and Australia. Some African countries such as Nigeria and Kenya have also entrenched devolution in their governance structures. In many cases, the quest for devolution has been driven by the need to bring government services close to the people in response to the growing pressure on reforms in the public sector and the desire for more inputs and representation in public affairs" management by citizens and equitable distribution of economic and political resources (Cheema & Rondinelli, 2007). Consequently, the global arena is full of illustrations of successful and not so successful experiments in decentralization.

Strategic change management is increasingly of important locally. Public organizations have continuously and repeatedly been faced with the need to change in order to render more efficient and better services to their citizens (Rossi, et al.,2022). Kenya's new Constitution envisages far-reaching changes encompassing transformation of the Kenyan state through new accountable and transparent institutions, inclusive approaches to government and a firm focus on equitable service delivery for all (World Bank, 2012). Counties in Kenya undertake their operations using very limited resources which have resulted to a lack of equipment, inadequate logistical capacity and weak operational preparedness (Board of Governors Conference, 2016). A study by Denrell (2004) on resources and returns examines the importance of analysing companies from resource side as opposed to the product side. According to Denrell, resources for example technology, brand names, trade contacts, skilled personnel, machinery, efficient procedures as well as capital form the basis for attainment and sustainability of change initiative that is strong as well as great firm performance.

According to ROK, (2015) the inauguration of the constitution of Kenya, 2010 saw gargantuan changes and transformation not only in the governance structure and system but also in the life of the Kenya citizens. Mwakamba & Theuri, (2016) states that this has fundamentally transitioned institutions largely nationalized into devolved units offering services and

goods much closer to the people. It meant that administrative units, economic and social services was devolved closer to the people. This transition brought in both fortunes and challenges in equal measure (UNDP, 2015), with challenges stemming unknown and uncharted environs of the new norm. Even though the new system premised on efficiency, responsiveness, accountability and democracy, little in these areas have been achieved (Ngigi & Busolo, 2019). Instead, the intra-governmental changes have been very slow, scattered and poorly planned (Ngigi, et al., 2019), weak leadership and insufficient utilization of strategic change management principles. This has resulted in cost inefficiencies, loses of funds, defunct projects and corruption (Ndalila, 2016). This mismatch between the expectation of the devolved system and the observed trends has been pinned on strategic change management (Kitsios & Kamariotou, 2017).

Kakucha, Simba and Anwar (2018) studied the impacts of organizational structure on strategic change management in West Pokot County Government. A descriptive cross-sectional survey design using qualitative and quantitative approaches was utilized. Their study realized that a positive and significant association existed between organizational structure and strategic change management. The study recommended that the county governments should focus on organizational structure since it contributes to a greater extent towards a change management process. Chepkemoi and Moronge (2015) in the study on organizational change management in the public sector in Kenya, argue that in change management one needs to understand major change components such as: what is changing, reasons for the change, those influenced by the change and the change management process. In addition, when the components of shared vision, skills, leadership, resources, incentives are strategy are collectively inherent, there is high possibility of change occurring (Rajapakse, 2015). In a study conducted by Obonyo and Kerongo (2015) on factors influencing strategic change management and the performance of Kenyan Commercial Banks, the organization culture is greatly associated with its management style, which of course was people centred. The same examination found out that interpersonal skill when it comes to the process of decision making and people engaged, worked out in favour of strategic change management implementation (Rossi, et al., 2022). Ichangi (2011) in his detailed strategic management documentation revealed that the central level management as well as the bottom one are charged with the organization responsibility of originating, defending and ensuring that every organizational member follows the development plans so as to accomplish the entire change management strategy in a gradual and seamless manner. Members in any organization are guided by organizational plans which act as a unifying factor and a bridge to the realization of the implemented strategic change management (Wan, et al. 2022).

Strategic change management is one of important areas in strategic management practices. For any firm's success there must be strategic change management applicable (Wan, et al. 2022). Obudo & Wario, (2015) states that change is an inevitable continuous process which establishes long-term direction as well as performance of organizations for ensuring careful formulation, effective implementation as well as continuous evaluation of strategy in progress. However, evidence suggests that a high proportion of strategic change initiatives fail causing significant resources impact where it is estimated that 15% of every dollar spent on strategic change initiatives is lost (Hughes, 2011; Kuipers, Kickert, & Higgs, 2013; Cabrey, Haughey, & Cooke-Davies, 2014). For successful implementation of organizational change to occur it calls for simultaneous changes in multiple organizational dimensions (By & Macleod, 2012). Public organizations have continuously and repeatedly been faced with the need to change in order to render more efficient and better services to their citizens. Kenyan 2010 Constitution envisages far-reaching changes encompassing transformation of the country via new institutions that are accountable and transparent, inclusive approaches to government as well as a serious focus on equitable service delivery to all citizens (World Bank, 2012). The national government requires county governments to rethink on how they undertake their businesses, do an assessment on the consequences of duplicating services and adopt ideal strategies that result in increased outcomes (GoK, 2003; Obongo, 2009). County governments in Kenya operate in high turbulence and have to position themselves in a strategic manner to adapt to the constantly changing operations in their public service delivery to the citizens. Numerous studies on corporate strategy have reported a correlation between strategic change management and performance in many commercial and non-profit organizations (Baini & Mwasiaji, 2018; Walter & Vincent. 2018). Poorly formulated strategy and improper implementation practices have been identified as the primary causes of dismal performances in many organizations (Riany, Were and Kihara, 2018). In Kenya, some firms continue to perform below stakeholder expectations. According to Walter and Vincent (2018), many of these firms have for quite some time either continuously reported poor performance, for instance Kenya Airways, Pan Paper Company and Mumias Sugar Company, while other including Uchumi Supermarkets collapsed and closed its operations (Riany, 2021). Even state-owned Institutions of higher learning that deals with knowledge creation and dissemination have reported financial distress and

delays in implementing various development projects provided for within their respective strategic plans (Njue & Ongoto, 2018; Mathooko and Ogutu, 2014).

The challenge of managing behavioural and systemic change has been a major issue in the Kenyan county governments. The devolved units have remained irrelevant in ensuring unmatched efficiency in service delivery (Jelagat, 2013). Unless strategy is translated into measures that employees can understand then it will be difficult to accept its functionality and this has been capitalised by poor management of resources, poor leadership styles, lack of strategy implementation and lots of resource misappropriations. Mwakamba and Theuri (2016) in their study on the role of change management strategies in effective devolution in the county government of Taita Taveta established that directive strategy as a change management strategy had a weak influence on devolution while the educative strategy and the participative strategy were very influential in the devolution process in the county. Therefore, the study sought to evaluate to determine the effect of leadership strategy on performance of the county government of West Pokot

2. LEADERSHIP STRATEGY

Organizations depend on capable leadership to guide them through unprecedented changes. Yet there's ample evidence that even some of the most established organizations are failing to adapt to change, implement their strategic plans successfully, or prepare for an uncertain future. A leadership strategy is a map that aligns investments in leadership development with the strategy, goals, and aspirations of the business. A leadership strategy makes explicit how many leaders are needed, what kind, where they're needed, with what skills, and behaving in what fashion, both individually and collectively to achieve the desired outcomes. It also identifies other issues the organization must consider, such as whether current talent systems (like onboarding or performance management) support the culture and leadership the organization wants to create (Center C.L. 2020).

Leadership is defined as the process of having an influence on others and agreeing on what requires to be accomplished and how it will be undertaken in an effective way and the collective efforts required to achieve the stated objectives (Yang, Zhao, and Baron 2007). Hellriegel and Slocum (1974) posit that change management requires embracement from leaders and staff who are compassionate. Keeping in mind that change is inevitable, the management has to develop a change management plan that guides the workers on the path to take so as to reach to a permanent change.

Effective strategic leadership is considered as a major ingredient for the successful performance of any organization operating in the ever dynamic and complex environment of the 21st century. In the context of information uncertainty and resource scarcity, strategic leadership is required to confront the reality of environmental turbulence and a continuous need for appropriate organizational change in order to achieve performance goals. The goal of any organization is not only to survive, but also to sustain its existence by improving performance. In order to meet the needs of the highly competitive markets, organizations must continually increase performance (Arslan & Staub 2013). Among the many roles of a leader in driving change is to own the vision and inspire the employees towards the realization of the firm's vision, and help employees in owning the same vision. Organizational change can be achieved when organizational leadership motivate their work teams towards this end (Strand, 2014). Mahdi and Almsafi (2014) supported this view by stating that effective leadership is core to producing an organization that is strategy focused, that ultimately helps in realizing the desired objective.

Prior literature suggests that role of leadership is critically important for achieving the performance of organizations (Boal & Hooijberg 2000; Peterson, Smith, Martorana & Owens 2003). The core purpose of strategic leadership theory and research is to understand how much influence top executives have over performance (Singh et al. 2016). Empirical and conceptual studies have shown that strategic leadership actions significantly influence performance (Quigley & Graffin, 2017; Ireland & Hitt, 1999). Unfortunately, other studies conclude that their actions are impeded by situational constraints, inertia or random effects, such that they don't have much leeway over performance (Fitza, 2017; Haveman, 1992). These divergent findings indicate either a lack of evidence in establishing a direct association between strategic leadership and performance or of the many confounding variables that make it difficult to demonstrate a clear cause and effect (Knies et al., 2016). An organisation's head would therefore have to inspire a transformation in the organization and implement ways on how to facilitate the process (Kimotho & Mwasiiji, 2019). This moves the process along by shaping the implementation plan (Hambrick & Wowak, 2021). According to Sila and Gichiga (2016), any decisions made by a leader must be strategic in nature. For a successful implementation of strategy, a thorough and careful considerations need to be instituted before

and during the process of implementing strategy. Intensive but considerate practices during strategy implementation process need to be carried out if the organization has to succeed.

Hambrick & Quigley (2014) point out that scholars are yet to agree on the conceptualization and operationalization of contextual conditions strategic leaders face. Various scholars have argued that methodological and statistical limitations, unavailability of relevant control variables and contexts have systematically undermined the effect of strategic leadership on performance (Fitza, 2017; Hambrick & Quigley, 2014; Blettner et al., 2012; Thomas, 1998). Boal & Hooijberg (2001) observe that studies on strategic leadership are limited since many have used demographic variables as substitutes for moderating or mediating variables. Crossan et al., (2008) argue that many studies have excluded critical organizational and environmental variables that might moderate or mediate such a relationship. Additionally, empirical literature has solely examined the impact of strategic leadership at the micro levels without integrating both the micro and macro perspectives of leadership (Bornardi et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2014).

Leadership assumes three dimensions of change namely; task-oriented leadership, change oriented leadership as well as relationship-oriented leadership. The main concern of the task-oriented leadership is accomplishing the task, maintaining orderly reliable operations and efficient utilization of resources (Hay and Hodgkinson 2006). Change oriented leadership focuses on adapting to change in the environment, improving strategic decisions, major changes in processes, increasing flexibility and innovation and committing to change. Senge et al (1999) argues that authority driven change is often effective in the short run, more efficient to organize and more convenient for most organizations. More fruits are reaped from change if the change effort is pushed. Organizations should invest in development of leadership in order to attain better performances. Nearly all firms engaging in change management have employed some form of leadership development strategies. Change management requires strong leadership to push through risky and stressful shifts in the business. Ideally, managers should understand when to change and the recommended time to seek stability, trigger a change or avoid change (De Wit and Meyer 2010).

In Bartoli and Blatrix's opinion (2015), the definition of performance should be achieved through items such as evaluation, piloting, efficiency, effectiveness and quality. Performance shows how well an organization has utilized the resources at its disposal in generating wealth for the shareholders. According to Wheleen and Hunger (2001), firm performance is the final result of a firm operating within the specified period (Delaney and Huselid, 1996). Organizational performance is measured using several variables including: quality of service delivered, quantity of output productivity, research and development, level of absenteeism and annual turnover (Hamon, 2003).

According to Luhangala and Anyieni (2019) the success of an organization is gauged from several indicators both qualitative and quantitative. These include: financial performance, meeting customer needs, building quality products and services, encouraging innovation and creativity and gaining employee commitment. Organizational performance of firms in Malaysia is determined by the actual output measured against intended goals and objectives. Therefore, it is important for the owners or managers of an organization to know the performance rate of their organization to be able to know what changes they can introduce (Lo, Wang, Wah & Ramayah, 2016). According to Al-Tit (2017) performance the firm operating in Malaysia can be understood by how well an organization is doing to achieve its goals. Therefore, it can be argued that without the knowledge of the performance, it will be difficult for the management of these firms to know when exactly changes are needed in the organization. Organizational performance includes strategic planning, operations, financial, legal, and organizational development. Lukorito (2015) revealed that communication was key to achieve positive strategic performance of the Kenya Airways Limited and is also found to involve the employees in decision making process through the open door policy hence motivating the employees. According to Goll and Rashid (2017) leadership is key to strategic performance of the organization and in a bid to correct deficiencies within organizations, leadership and senior management resolve to a lot of alternatives: training, team building, re-engineering and even rationalization; all these strategies are aimed at ensuring organizations remain not only dominant but competitively dominant. McIvor, Humphreys, Wall and McKittrick (2013) proposed that firms delivering services must broaden their examination of productivity from the conventional company-oriented perspective to a dual company-customer perspective. This broadened approach can help reconcile conflicts or leverage synergies between improving service quality and boosting service productivity.

Organization performance checks the efficiency of management in the utilization of resources entrusted to them by the shareholders in generating wealth within a given time period (Berger and Patti, 2002). It is measured by ratios at different points in time to establish how well the resources of the firm have been applied in generating wealth. Different ratios have

been applied depending on the purpose of the measurement. According to Berger and Patti (2002), ratios indicate if the firm is utilizing the resources at its disposal in achieving the objective set by the owners of a business of making them wealthier. The ratios are used to standardize measurement so as to enable comparison across the industry, same firm over a period of years or other firms in other industries.

Performance measures can be grouped into two basic types: those that relate to results (outputs or outcomes such as competitiveness or financial performance) and those that focus on determinants of the results (inputs such as quality, flexibility, resource utilization, and innovation). This suggests that performance framework can be built around the concepts of results and determinants, (Gunasekaran, 2019). Many firms are struggling to implement their corporate strategy. Raps and Kauffman (2015) expounds that the problem is shown by the indecisive low-level performance which is approximately 10% to 30% of envisioned strategies. Bititci et al (2015) additionally argued that most organizations are stunted before expected advantages are understood as the strategy moves into execution stage. Fruitful implementation is a challenge that requires the managers to have patience, determinations and energy. The implementation process integrative view is essential for success (Raps and Kauffman, 2015) Strategic management scholars, in their mission for establishing performance associations of the strategic behaviour of businesses, continue to measure performance of the business using a broad range of operationalizing schemes (Mugambi and K'Obonyo, 2017).

Organizational performance is concerned with the overall productivity in an organization in terms of stock turnover, customers, profitability and market share. The concept of organizational performance is core to businesses because the major objective of businesses is to make profits. Iravo et. al., (2013) state that one of the important questions in business has been why some organizations succeed and why others fail and this has influenced a study on the drivers of organizational performance. Fwaya (2006) views performance as a formula for the assessment of the functioning of an organization under certain parameters such as productivity, employee' morale and effectiveness. Nzuve and Nyaega (2012) opined that Performance management and improvement is at the heart of strategic management because a lot of strategic thinking is geared towards defining and measuring performance. Awino (2011) asserts that for an organization to be successful it has to record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization. Odhiambo (2009) identified three approaches to performance in an organization which are the goal approach, which states that an organization pursues definite identifiable goals. This approach describes performance in terms of the attainment of these goals. The second approach is the systems resource approach which defines performance as a relationship between an organization and its environment. This concept defines performance according to an organization's ability to secure the limited and valued resources in the environment. The third approach is the process perspective which defines performance in terms of the behaviour of the human resource of an organization (Waiganjo et. al., 2012). Kiragu (2005) highlights performance in terms of four perspectives which are the financial, customer, internal processes and innovativeness. The financial perspective identifies the key financial drivers of enhancing performance which are profit margin, asset turnover, leverage, cash flow, and working capital (Odhuno and Wadongo, 2010).

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3. METHOD

This study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population for the study comprised of management and a supervisory cadre within county government of West Pokot, Kenya. Since the study population was small, the study worked with entire population which is census. Data collection instrument applied questionnaire. A structured questionnaire was administered to the respondents. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of data collection instrument. The data was organized, coded, edited, classified using a table and analyzed to bring out the meaning under each of the factors. The objective was to construct a systematic account of what has been recorded, and by so doing construct a theory around the problem statement. Once data is collected, it was crosschecked and verified for errors, completeness and consistency. It was coded, entered and analysed descriptively using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 28). Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between variables. ANOVA and multiple linear regression analysis was adopted computed to determine the statistical relationship between the independent variable and the dependent.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The specific objective of the study was to determine the effect of leadership strategy on performance of County Government of West Pokot. The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on statements relating to determine the effect of leadership strategy on performance of County Government of West Pokot. A 5-point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in Table 1.

From the results, the respondents agreed that the organization should embrace task-oriented leadership to accomplishing the task, maintaining orderly reliable operations and efficient utilization of resources. This is supported by a mean of 4.231 (std. dv = 0.943). In addition, as shown by a mean of 4.862 (std. dv = 0.876), the respondents agreed that the organization should embrace change-oriented leadership who focuses on adapting to change in the environment, improving strategic decisions, major changes in processes, increasing flexibility and innovation and committing to change. Further, the respondents agreed that organizations should invest in development of leadership in order to attain better performances. This is shown by a mean of 3.831 (std. dv = 0.944).

The respondents also agreed that change management requires strong leadership to push through risky and stressful shifts in the business. This is shown by a mean of 3.986 (std. dv = 0.935). The respondents also agreed that managers should understand when to change and the recommended time to seek stability, trigger a change or avoid change. This is shown by a mean of 3.321 (std. dv = 0.914). Finally, the respondents also agreed that leadership strategy enhances organisational performance which is shown by a mean of 3.838 (std.dev 0.921).

Table 4.1: Leadership Strategy on Performance of CGWP

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
The organization should embrace task-oriented leadership to accomplishing the task, maintaining orderly reliable operations and efficient utilization of resources	64	4.231	0.943
The organization should embrace change-oriented leadership who focuses on adapting to change in the environment, improving strategic decisions, major changes in processes, increasing flexibility and innovation and committing to change	64	4.862	0.876
Organizations should invest in development of leadership in order to attain better performances	64	3.831	0.944
Change management requires strong leadership to push through risky and stressful shifts in the business	64	3.986	0.935
managers should understand when to change and the recommended time to seek stability, trigger a change or avoid change	64	3.321	0.914
Leadership strategy enhances organisational performance	64	3.838	0.921
Aggregate		3.782	0.886

(Source: Researcher 2024)

4.1 Performance of CGWP

The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on various statements relating to the performance of West Pokot County Government Kenya. A 5-point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in Table 4.2.

From the results, the respondents agreed that there is presence of efficiency in utilization of resources in County Government of West Pokot. This is supported by a mean of 4.186 (std. dv = 0.994). In addition, as shown by a mean of 3.917 (std. dv = 0.831), the respondents agreed that customer satisfaction is the organisational priority in County Government of West Pokot. Further, the respondents agreed that the main strategic change management enhances provision of better services in County Government of West Pokot. This is shown by a mean of 3.858 (std. dv = 0.563). The respondents also agreed that Strategic change management enhances provision of Infrastructure development in County Government of West Pokot. This is shown by a mean of 3.831 (std. dv = 0.851). Lastly, the results shows that strategic change management enhances provision of service delivery in county government of West Pokot. This was supported by a mean of 3.411 (std. dv = 0.644).

Table 4.2: Performance of County Government of West Pokot

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
There is presence of efficiency in utilization of resources in county government of West Pokot	64	4.186	0.994
Customer satisfaction is the organizational priority in county government of West Pokot	64	3.917	0.831
Strategic change management enhances provision of better services in county government of West Pokot	64	3.858	0.563
Strategic change management enhances provision of Infrastructure development in county government of West Pokot	64	3.831	0.851
Strategic change management enhances provision of service delivery in county government of West Pokot	64	3.411	0.644
There is elaborate performance measurement mechanism at the County Government of West Pokot	64	3.321	0.713
Aggregate		3.835	0.868

(Source: Researcher 2024)

4.2 Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics in the current study focused on correlation and regression analysis. Correlation analysis was used to determine the strength of the relationship while regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between dependent variable (Performance of County Government of West Pokot) and independent variables (leadership strategy).

4.2.1 Correlation Analysis

This study used Pearson correlation analysis to determine the strength of association between independent variables (leadership strategy) and the dependent variable (Performance of County Government of West Pokot). Pearson correlation coefficient range between zero and one, where by the strength of association increase with increase in the value of the correlation coefficients. The current study employed Taylor (2018) correlation coefficient ratings where by 0.80 to 1.00 depicts a very strong relationship, 0.60 to 0.79 depicts strong, 0.40 to 0.59 depicts moderate, 0.20 to 0.39 depicts weak.

Table 4.3: Correlation Coefficients

		Performance of County Government of West Pokot		Leadership strategy	
Performance of County Government of West Pokot	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	64			
Leadership strategy	Pearson Correlation	.854**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002			
	N	64		64	

From the results on table 4-12, there was a very strong relationship between leadership strategy and (Performance of County Government of West Pokot ($r = .854$, p value =0.002). The relationship was significant since the p value 0.002 was less than 0.05 (significant level).

4.2.2 Regression Analysis

Multivariate regression analysis was used to assess the relationship between independent variables (leadership strategy, strategy implementation, resource allocation, organization culture) and the dependent variable (Performance of County Government of West Pokot) as shown on table 4.4 below.

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.943 ^a	.826	.881	.11639

a. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Strategy

The model summary was used to explain the variation in the dependent variable that could be explained by the independent variables. The r-squared for the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable was 0.881. This implied that 88.1% of the variation in the dependent variable (Performance of County Government of West Pokot) could be explained by independent variable (leadership strategy).

Table 4.5: Analysis of Variance

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	22.028	1	3.022	46.39	.000 ^b
1	Residual	7.511	64	.034		
	Total	29.539	65			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of County Government of West Pokot

b. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Strategy.

(Source: Researcher 2024)

The ANOVA was used to determine whether the model was a good fit for the data. F calculated was 46.39. The p value was 0.000. Therefore, the model can be used to predict the influence of leadership strategy, strategy implementation, prudent resource allocation, organization culture on Performance of County Government of West Pokot.

Table 4.6: Regression Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		β	Std. Error	β		
1	(Constant)	0.482	0.036		5.103	0.000
	Leadership strategy	0.674	0.092	0.394	3.451	0.004

a Dependent Variable: Performance of County Government of West Pokot

(Source: Researcher 2024)

The regression model was as follows:

$$Y = 0.482 + 0.674X_1 + \varepsilon$$

According to the results on table 4-13, leadership strategy has a significant effect on Performance of County Government of West Pokot ($\beta_1=0.674$, p value= 0.004). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.004 was less than the significant level of 0.05.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The specific objective of the study was to determine the effect of leadership strategy on performance of County Government of West Pokot. The findings revealed that the organization should embrace task-oriented leadership to accomplishing the task, maintaining orderly reliable operations and efficient utilization of resources and that the organization should embrace change-oriented leadership who focuses on adapting to change in the environment, improving strategic decisions, major changes in processes, increasing flexibility and innovation and committing to change. This finding add weight to the findings by Westenholz, 2018 who concluded that in today's business evolvment, change is constant and organizational leaders who anticipate change and react rapidly to it are successful. Further, the revealed that organizations should invest in development of leadership in order to attain better performances and that change management requires strong leadership to push through risky and stressful shifts in the business. The findings also indicated that managers should understand when to change and the recommended time to seek stability, trigger a change or avoid change and that leadership strategy enhances organisational performance. The findings are in tandem with Tyssen, Wald and Spieth (2014) who revealed that leadership is one of the key factors necessary to attain a desired level of performance in an organization.

Based on the findings, the study concluded that leadership strategy has a significant effect on Performance of County Government of West Pokot $\beta_1=0.674$, p value= 0.004). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.004 was less than the significant level of 0.05.

The study came up with the following recommendations; The county government should embrace task-oriented leadership who focuses on adapting to change in the environment, improving strategic decisions, major changes in processes, increasing flexibility and innovation and committing to change to accomplishing the task, maintaining orderly reliable operations and efficient utilization of resources

The county governments should understand when to change and the recommended time to seek stability, trigger a change or avoid change and that leadership strategy enhances organisational performance

They should be Implementation of effective, transparent goal-setting management strategies to improve effectiveness by highlighting redundancy, improving common understanding, and providing visible criteria for making decisions; all of which support improved coordination since organisation success depends on the financial capacity to implement strategies proper communication during the strategic plan implementation process.

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